

*“Stealing the Hearts of Israel”
Rhetoric, Ambition and Performance
The Calculated Pause of Absalom, 2 Samuel 15:4*

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the pause in Absalom’s speech at 2 Samuel 15:4 and argues that the silence forms part of his calculated political performance. Set against the narrative of Absalom’s gradual campaign to “steal the hearts of the men of Israel”, the essay explores how gesture, diction, syntax and audience-shift combine to portray ambition disguised as justice. Particular attention is given to the chiasmic structure of the speech, the emphatic first-person expressions, the unusual use of על, and the third-person suffix in והצדקתי. The pause is interpreted as a dramatic moment of self-presentation, manipulation and concealed royal aspiration.

2 Samuel 15:4

וַיֹּאמֶר אֲבִשָׁלוֹם מִיִּשְׁמֹנֵי שֶׁפֶט בְּאַרְצוֹ וְעָלִי יָבֹא כָּל־אִישׁ אֲשֶׁר־יְהִי־לִוְיָבִיב וּמִשֶּׁפֶט וְהִצַּדַּקְתִּי

We might have spent too much time analysing the context to this pause, but we did find it fascinating, and we hope that it all fed into our eventual conclusions.

After murdering Amnon, Absalom had run away from Israel to his maternal family’s kingdom (13:37, 38). Joab, who had a reputation for protecting David’s kingdom from those who would threaten it, decided that an insurrection was a possibility and that having Absalom in Jerusalem was preferable so that he could be watched more closely (14:21).

Joab was right. Back in Jerusalem, “Absalom proceeded to have a chariot made

for himself, with horses and with fifty men running before him” (verse 1). All this public pomp and pageantry was the first part of Absalom’s campaign—to increase his visibility and to show his suitability for the throne (1 Samuel 8:11). Adonijah went on to do the same thing, “And his father did not hurt his feelings at any time by saying: ‘Why is this the way you have done?’” (1 Kings 1:5, 6). This created the impression that the king was giving his approval, so that Adonijah and Absalom drew supporters to his side.

The second part of Absalom’s campaign was aimed at increasing his popularity. The “handshaking and baby circuit” refers to the traditional grassroots efforts politicians make to connect with the public. This involves events where they meet voters face-to-face, shake hands, kiss babies and engage in conversations to build rapport and support. All this requires a significant investment of time and energy striving to make a lasting, positive impression on a wide variety of voters. No wonder Absalom had to spend long days in his quest.

Verse 2:

And Absalom rose up early and stood at the side of the road to the gate. And it came about, when any man happened to have a legal case to come to the king for judgment, then Absalom would call him and say: “From what city are you?” and he would say: “From one of the tribes of Israel your servant is.”

The scene was the gate to the king’s palace. Absalom was up early, maybe to show his industriousness and diligence, and maybe to head off as many as possible before they could have their audience with the king.

We have seen that Absalom is patient (2 Samuel 13:23). And if we are to take the reference in verse 7 to be four years (LXX, Sy, Vg), then Absalom may have met hundreds, maybe thousands of people at the king’s gate.

Industriousness, diligence, patience. If Absalom had added humility, then Jehovah could have used him to benefit his fellow Israelite.

He would begin his interaction by calling out, “From what city are you?” It would seem that his aim was to find common ground, show interest, make a connection. Once he had found out where they lived, Absalom would perhaps relate his familiarity with the place and someone they might mutually know and hence he could convey his understanding and then affinity for the person. This meant that the plaintiff felt a sort of chummy allegiance, as if Absalom was on their side.

In response to “From what city are you?”, the person is reported to respond by telling Absalom from what *tribe* they came from. Perhaps they started with the tribe and went on to the city/town. Or Absalom had not heard of the city/town so the tribe was mentioned. Israelites were identified strongly with their tribe.¹ Certainly, the mention of the tribe reinforced Absalom’s attempts to position himself as a leader for all Israel, aiming to create a sense of solidarity and inclusivity that transcended city loyalties and spoke to larger, collective identities.

In verse 5 we learn:

It also occurred that, when a man drew near to bow down to him, he thrust his hand out and grabbed hold of him and kissed him.

The kiss was meant to express congruence, harmony and affection.

Verse 3:

And Absalom would say to him: “See, your matters are good and straight; but there is no one from the king giving you a hearing”.

Davis (p. 188) paints the scene well:

He worked the crowd.... Absalom would inquire about his new friend’s hometown, furrow his brow in apparent concentration as he listened to the fellow’s dilemma, periodically injecting a grunt of empathy, then indicate how cogent he thought the case was. In fact, Absalom never met a plaintiff with whom he didn’t agree.

And that is something that no judge could promise. All the more so here, where Absalom probably met the other litigants in the case.

Absalom began this speech not with הִנֵּה, but with הֲאֵלֶיךָ. He was not making an exclamation, but an appeal to the person to understand, to know, to be reassured.

The narrator does not belabour the story with every tale that Absalom heard, he only tells us Absalom’s words. But this probably implies that Absalom did little listening and all the talking, which is ironic since Absalom claimed that there was no one to hear the case. Pride does not want to serve but only the honour.

A few commentators use the word demagogue—someone who seeks to gain power and influence by appealing to the emotions, prejudices and fears rather than using reasoned arguments. No judge could promise that *everyone* would win their

1. Numbers 1:1–4; 36:7–9; Joshua 7:16–18; Judges 20:1, 2.

case if he heard it.² But it is quite some emotive combination—the power display by the chariot and the attendants, then the promises.

He also threw in an “insinuation that the king was careless about the administration of justice” (Smith). David might have been ill at this time. *The Watchtower* says that Psalm 41 could have been written at this time (2015 12/15 p. 24). But not for four years, so it might have been that Absalom took advantage of the situation at the beginning of David’s illness.

Ironically, the Tekoite woman had said to David: “My lord is wise as with the wisdom of the angel of the [true] God so as to know all that is in the earth” (14:20).

Why did Absalom pause mid-speech? Here is the speech before and after:

רָאָה דְבָרֶיךָ טוֹבִים וְנִכְחִים

A *See, your matters are good and straight*

וְשָׁמַע אִירֶלֶךְ מֵאֵת הַמֶּלֶךְ

B *but there is no one from the king giving you a hearing*

מִיִּשְׁמָנִי שֹׁפֵט בְּאֶרֶץ וְעָלִי יָבוֹא כָּל־אִישׁ אֲשֶׁר־יִהְיֶה־לּוֹרֵיב וּמִשְׁפָּט

B' *O that I were appointed judge in the land, that to me every man might come that happens to have a legal case or judgment!*

וְהִצַּדִּקְתִּי

A' *Then I should certainly do justice to him.*

We can see that there is a chiasmus. The understanding in A, “See, your matters are good and straight”, means that Absalom promises that he would give the plaintiff a favourable judgement A’: “Then I should certainly do justice to him”. Then with his inner lines B/B’, Absalom replaced the king with himself as judge, and he replaced the absence of a hearing (the king) with an open door (himself)—the opportunity for *everyone*, to come that happens to have a legal case. He appealed to people’s frustrations with the justice system by pledging that he would be an approachable, fair, relatable and attentive judge. There is no doubt that he wanted to replace the king, but he just about hid this ambition from his audience by replacing the word “king” with “judge”.

We also see in verse 4 the triple use of the first person: I, me, I. The accusative

2. Fokkelman contrasts Absalom’s form of justice with the preceding chapter where David is portrayed as the ideal judge, and ironically judging in favour of Absalom (p. 168).

pronoun “me” is actually emphasised in the phrase וְעָלִי יָבוֹא, since the standard order would be יָבוֹא עָלַי, which would place the emphasis on the action. Instead, Absalom said something like: to *me* let him come.

And, in this invitation he did not use אֶל, ‘to’, but עַל, literally ‘upon’. His use of that preposition might imply that he was promising—albeit falsely—his full engagement in the person’s legal process, that he would *take on* the responsibility of the person’s case.

The *maqfeh* is usually used to link two words, but here there is an unusual grouping of *four* words: אֲשֶׁר־יִהְיֶה־לְרִיב, “that/he will be/to him/a case”. This creates a certain uninterrupted flow. We got the impression that Absalom had repeated his script so often that the words were eliding—much like a sales script that has been recited day after day.

What was going on in the pause?

We believe that the key lies in Absalom’s last word in verse 4, וְהִצְדַּקְתִּי. This is the *Hiphil* perfect of צָדַק, to administer justice. Absalom used the perfect to express his certainty. But notice the suffixed pronoun. It is not as would be expected—the second person singular. Verse 4 is not addressed to Absalom’s immediate audience, but the pronoun is the third person singular: I would administer justice for *him*.

After saying, “there is no one from the king giving you a hearing”, it looks as if Absalom used the pause to adjust his audience. Did he lose all semblance of interest in the man at his feet? Did he think as he paused, this man is far too small, too particular; my ambition is greater, I want *all* to hear my appeal? Did he raise his head and announce to all who were around: מִי־יִשְׁמְנֵי שֹׁפֵט בְּאֶרֶץ, “O that I were appointed judge in the land”. GKC explain that this form of exclamation with מִי followed by the imperfect is an unfulfilled but possible wish, and hence also, that which is desired, translating the phrase literally as, “who maketh me judge?”, adding, i.e., “O that I were made judge!” (§151 *a*).

Or, perhaps Absalom meant this speech to seem as if it was now to all around, but he was still focusing on the individual at his feet. If so, he wanted the litigant to know that when he became judge he could take on *all* injustices, hoping that the litigant would understand that his issue was well within Absalom’s capabilities to resolve for his benefit.

Or did Absalom use the pause to adjust his volume? Did he utter the words in

verse 4 *sotto voce*? Did he make it sound like the claimant had become so close to him, so intimate, that he was now being admitted into his private thoughts, into his soliloquy.

Or even better, did he pause, close his eyes and utter a faux prayer, so that the man was shown a display of Absalom's piety and his desire that God would help him achieve this justice that he had promised for all?

Absalom may have come back into Israel under a cloud of suspicion, guilty of killing his brother and obviously disapproved of by David, but he went about transforming himself into a hero in the public mind (Evans, p. 231). "And Absalom kept stealing the hearts of the men of Israel" (verse 6).

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Davis Dale Ralph Davis, *2 Samuel—Out of Every Adversity*, Christian Focus, 1999.
- Evans Mary J. Evans, *The Message of Samuel—Personalities, potential, politics and power*, Inter-Varsity Press, 2004.
- Fokkelman . . . J.P. Fokkelman, *Narrative Art and Poetry in the Books of Samuel, King David*, Volume I, Van Gorcum, 1981.
- GKC Gesenius' *Hebrew Grammar*, Wilhelm Gesenius, edited and enlarged by Emil Kautzsch, translated into English by Arthur Ernest Cowley, Oxford, 1910.
- LXX *Old Testament in Greek According to the Septuagint*, F. H. A. Scrivener and H.B. Swete, Cambridge, 1909.
- Sy Syriac *Peshitta*.
- Vg *Vulgate*.
- w *The Watchtower*, Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.